

Modeling And Forecasting Of Petroleum Pump Price Fluctuation In The Event Of The Subsidy Removal Using Robust-Garch (GM-Estimators) Model

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria the 10th largest oil producing country in the world have recently removed it petroleum subsidy, leading to significant fluctuations in the petroleum pump prices. Many studies have attempted to model and forecast petroleum pump prices using various non-robust approaches, including time-varying parameter models, machine learning techniques, hybrid models, and traditional time series models such as GARCH and ARCH models. However, these models assume normality and may not adequately account for complexities and potential non-linearities in the dynamic petroleum pump prices especially in the aftermath of the subsidy removal. This study aims at modifying a Robust-GARCH (GM-estimators) model, a robust estimation approach that accounts for heavy-tailed distributions and outliers, which can offer a potential solution to model the volatility of petroleum pump prices more accurately. The study uses the petroleum pump price, exchange rate and inflation rate average monthly data for the year 2000-2023. The result form the analysis shows that the GM-estimators-GARCH model predicts a steady increase in petroleum pump price over the next two years and petroleum pump price has an impact on the Nigerian standard of living, and that the GM-estimators GARCH model is fitted to forecast the future petroleum pump price volatility, having a lower RMSE of 20.2163, MSE of 3.5454 and MSE value of 408.69888. this gives the idea of the model's forecasting efficacy.

Keywords: forecasting efficacy, petroleum subsidy, non-robust approaches

INTRODUCTION

Petroleum pump price has been in the news and has attracted a lot of studies and analyses due to its many impacts on the economy's economic sectors and households. As the 10th largest oil producing country, Nigeria has witnessed a recent oscillation in petrol pump prices after eradicating the scandalous petrol subsidy. The policy change has left a spot for inflationary pressure and therefore calls for accurate modeling and future petroleum pump price forecast rise. Nevertheless, bitumen, kerosene, diesel, natural gas and the like are extracted from petroleum usually referred to as crude oil ((Dharam 1991). After almost a century of search and discovery the first commercial oil was discovered in 1956 at Oloibiri in the present day Bayelsa state Nigeria (Agbede, 2013). Petroleum product we have in our possession today is among the rarest natural resources and is easily available in our nation. Products obtained from petroleum are basic necessity for daily, individual, industrial and national operations. Petroleum product are used as automotive fuel by Nigerians and other people in the world in their cars, as source of electricity through generators sets, in industries and for cooking. Petroleum has remained Nigerians main industry contributing more than 14% to the country's GDP and accounting for 90% of the country's gross earning, 80% of budgetary revenue ,95% of foreign exchange earnings (Azaiki, 2007). (Usman, Ikemefuna, & Fatima, 2015), The Nigerian petroleum sector is one of the main revenues of the Nigerian economy and contributes largely to the development of Nigeria. In the last decades, the important Privileged and critical role that the Petroleum Industry plays in the generation of Nigeria's foreign exchange profits, also become a major source of domestic wealth (Azaiki, 2007). In the view of

Olaleye Sunday Samuel (2022) on oil Nigeria's revenue Source: Over 70 percent of the total government revenue is derived from petroleum products.

Aside from this, petroleum has made numerous and diverse contributions to national growths, including the creation of jobs, foreign exchange profits, income, industrialization and improvements to other economic variables and sectors. However, oil has dominated Nigeria's exports, 25% of its GDP. And 80% of its overall government revenue come from the country's oil reserves. Nigeria's central bank (2010). The national bureau of Statistics (NBS) data bulletin states that ₦4,026.18 billion (78.48%) of the entire value in Q3 2021 came from crude oil shipment which continues to dominate the export trade structure.

In Nigeria, the continual and frequent price hikes of petroleum products has attracted concerns, conflict and occasionally controversy. According to Olorunfemi (2010), petroleum prices have been increased by several Nigerian governments since Nigeria's independence to date.

As stated by Sanni, M. I. (2014), the federal government asserted that the primary reason for Nigeria's petroleum distribution issues and price instability is the existence of subsidies, that the selling price of petroleum per litre is less than the permitted profit margins, production costs, and distribution costs. Thus, the difference that the government bears constitutes the subsidy portion. When Akinwale et al. (2013) examined the economic effects of gradually eliminating petroleum subsidies in Nigeria, they found that while wages per capital showed a positive correlation with petroleum use, there was a negative correlation between the two. In Nigeria, the unpredictable increase in petroleum pump price began in the 1970s (Philip & Akintoye, 2006). This has been explained by several theories. In addition to the official petroleum pump price increase made by succeeding government under the pretext of "subsidy removal", there are other unlawful price increases that take place for a variety of reasons, such as the regular attack on oil installations, oil spills, sabotage from bunkers, and the kidnapping of foreign personnel's by militants in the Niger delta region (Sulaiman 1998).

The Nigerian government has faced multiple withdrawals of the government subsidies, with President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan's proposal in 2012 being reversible due to increase in the price of petrol and legal disputes and Nigeria rallies (Punch Newspaper 6th October 2023). Previous governments' attempt to eliminate the petroleum subsidy cause protest and strong opposition. President Bola Ahmed Tinubu abolished the longstanding petrol subsidy in Nigeria after taking office in May 29 2023, which caused the average retail price paid by consumers for premium motor spirit (PMS) in June 2023 which rose to ₦545.83, indicating an increase of 210.31% related to the value recorded in June 2022 (₦175.89). Likewise, comparing the average price valued with the previous month of May 2023, where the average retail price increases by 129.23% from ₦238.11. Since the country's refineries are not operating, refined petroleum products must be continuously imported, which puts a strain on the local currency.

The removal of petrol subsidy could potentially reduce transportation cost by 10% but it could also increase inflation rate to almost 19%. Doguwa and Alade (2023) suggested that this could lead to a significant increase in public transportation cost. The removal of petrol subsidy could also impact the agricultural industry, leading to increase in food prices and affecting the manufacturing process. Nweze & Edeme, (2016) highlights the significant impact of oil prices on Nigeria's economy, as oil exports accounts for 75% of government revenue. Cheke et al. (2011) argued that rising petroleum prices hurt both producers and consumers, affecting job creation and the survival of small medium enterprises (SME).

Financial time series frequently show signs of clustering, including stock prices, exchange rate, inflation rates and oil prices, among other factors. Other terms for this phenomenon is volatility clustering, where prices exhibit large fluctuations over a long period before showing comparatively calmer conditions afterward, which is relevant to nearly all microeconomic.

Similarly, empirical evidences have also demonstrated that the price of oil is among the most volatile, significantly influencing the macroeconomic behaviour of many industrialized and emerging nations (Federer, 1996, Guo & Kliesen 2005). Other scholars who have discovered volatility clustering and confirmed the existence of asymmetric in oil price volatility includes Mork, Olsen, and Mysen (1994), Hooker (1999), Gou and Kliesen (2005), Narayan (2007), Mehara (2008), Salisu and Fasanya (2013).

Researchers have continued to explore various approaches in tackling the challenges of volatility modeling, ranging from traditional time series models to more advanced statistical techniques. Numerous studies have made noteworthy significant contributions in the field of crude oil and petroleum price volatility modeling. For example, Monday, E. T. & A. Ahmed, (2020), model the fluctuation of crude oil price in Nigeria using ARCH and ARCH-M model, using monthly data over the period May 1989 to April 2019. The study examines the effect of oil price volatility, and demand for foreign exchange and external reserve on exchange rate volatility in Nigeria.

Similarly, Atanu E. Etuk, E. & Amos E. (2021) compare the performance of ARIMA and GARCH models in forecasting for crude oil price volatility from 2000 to 2012. Isyaka Mohammad Sanni, also investigated the effects of price fluctuations on the distribution of petroleum products in Gwagwalada.

Xu, F. et al (2018) employed petroleum pump price in China to develop a hybrid ARIMA_LSTM model, though the hybrid approach provides accurate forecasts, both the ARIMA and LSTM models fails to address the skewed and heavy-tailed distribution often associated with petroleum pump price data.

The study conducted by Anthony and Akaniynene (2022) utilized several generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity models to model the volatility of crude oil production as well as prices in Nigeria. The findings indicated that there was a causal connection between the two variables. This provides more evidence that each regime of oil price shock corresponds to a significant degree of production variability, which ultimately impedes the affected nation's economic growth.

Akpaeti et al. (2023), have used the multivariate Vector Error Correction technique to analyze pass-through adjustment in the context of gas pump prices' changes and customers' behavior in Nigeria in the period 1970–2016. The research found out that there was a short-term relationship between customer behavior and the price of gas at the pump as well as a long-term relationship. Therefore, the mobility and the cost of gasoline have negative and direct consequences on the attendant short –and- long-term behavioral interactions as also the macroeconomic policy factors such as; Importation of food, Foreign private investment, exchange rate fluctuations and Government funding to agriculture.

In addition, Gasper L. et al. (2023) attempt to tackle the challenge of forecasting crude oil prices in an atypical environment. This study examined a monthly trend of the Brent oil price from January 2002 to February 2022 using the Box Jenkins approach. Upon reaching step stationarity, the data were differenced, while selecting the models of analysis based on residual and ACF analysis. After the models' comparison it was established that the best model for prediction of the price of the crude oil was ARIMA (0, 1, 1). They advised further research, which shows that even while the coronavirus and the conflict in Ukraine have had a significant impact on crude oil prices, such a model is still able to capture the underlying volatility in crude oil prices.

In an attempt to model and forecast for petroleum pump prices, Dong and Cao (2023) developed a wavelet based GARCH_MIDAS model. However, they had included high and low frequency components into their model to extract, it is based on the GARCG framework, which presumes the normal distribution of return and, therefore, can be sensitive to the heavy-tailed and outlier.

Usman M. et al (2023) examine the relationship pattern of gasoline prices in several ASEAN countries: Indonesia, Malaysia, and Vietnam, and forecasted for the price of gasoline in the three countries for the next 12 months using a multivariate time series approach; first, the best vector autoregressive (VAR(p)) model was built based on Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC). Based on the best VAR(p) model, granger-causality analysis was discussed, and for forecasting gasoline prices, a state space model was developed in the study based on the best VAR(p). State vectors are built based on canonical correlation analysis. Based on the results of granger causality analysis, gasoline prices in Indonesia are affected by past gasoline prices in Vietnam; gasoline prices in Malaysia are affected by past gasoline prices in Indonesia and Vietnam.

Xin J. H., (2023) forecasted for gasoline pump price in US and analyzes its managerial implications by means of both univariate and multivariate time series forecasting models. The findings reveals that the time series regression model with trend, season, GDP, CPI, and crude oil price turns out the be the best forecasting model both on the training data and the testing data, even with the testing data containing significant turning points.

Petroleum pump prices and other variables were jointly forecasted by Zhao and Zhang (2023) using a capsule-based multivariate volatility model. As with many models that aim to manage dependencies among multiple time series

Sofianos, E. et al (2024) forecasted New York and Los Angeles gasoline price in daily frequency using three based machine learning Algorithm learning algorithms: decision trees, random forest, and XGBoost. Furthermore, a variable importance measure (VIM) technique was applied to identify and rank the most important explanatory variables. The optimal model, a trained random forest, achieves a mean absolute percent error (MAPE) in the out-of-sample of 3.23% for the New York and 3.78% for the Los Angeles gasoline spot prices.

Enstesar, H, I et al (2024) forecasted petroleum pump price using the adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS)the model uses a comprehensive dataset from the U.S anergy information administration spanning 30 years historical data from 1993 to 2023.

Ghaffar, A et al. (2024), analyzed petroleum price and diesel volatility in Pakistan from January 2010 to October 2023 using ARCH and GARCH models, where the findings reveals that petrol has higher volatility than diesel price and that both petrol and diesel prices showed significant ARCH and GARCH effects at 1% significance level.

Therefore, to address these limitations, this study proposed the use of the Robust-GARCH (GM-estimators) otherwise GM-GARCH model, a robust estimation approach that accounts for heavy-tailed distributions and outliers by assuming a mixture of normal distributions. By incorporating the GM-GARCH model, this study aims to provide

a comprehensive modeling framework than can more accurately capture the fluctuations in petroleum pump price in Nigeria following the removal of the petroleum subsidy.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Currently Nigeria is the 10th largest oil producer internationally and as such it recently deregulated the petrol subsidy which has led to inflation in Nigeria. Trimming of this subsidy has, therefore, caused disparities in the petroleum pump prices, which have broad based economic and social impacts. To aid policy makers, and other related stakeholders, the modelling and forecasting of such prices changes is extremely important.

Other recent studies (for example; Xin J. H., 2023; Usman M. et al., 2023; Sofianos, E. et al., 2024; Enstesar, H, I et al., 2024; Ghaffar, A et al., 2024) attempted to model and forecast petroleum pump prices using number of non-robust methods, which include time-varying parameter models, machine learning methods, hybrid models and the standard GARCH and ARCH models. Where such models assume normality and could not account for heavy-tailed distribution and outliers commonly observed in petroleum price data.

Therefore, to accurately model the volatility of petroleum pump prices, this study proposed a modified GARCH model which is the GM-GARCH, a robust estimation approach that account for heavy-tailed distribution and outliers. The GM-estimators GARCH model can improve the model's outstanding performance in detecting non-normal and heavy-tailed distribution, which is typical of such petroleum pump price data. Thus, this study seeks to build on the study of Ghaffar et al., (2024) by proposing a more robust modeling framework approach that adopts the GM-estimators GARCH model in capturing the volatility of the petroleum pump price in Nigeria after removal of petrol subsidy.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The goal of this research is to modify the GARCH model developed by Bollerslev, Tim, (1986) to become more resistance to outlier and heavy-tailed distribution so as to accurately estimate the future petroleum pump price (PMS). The specific objectives are to:

- I. determine the forecasting accuracy of the modified model compared to the existing models;
- II. to use the improved GM-estimator GARCH models in forecasting for the future petroleum pump price for the next 24 months ahead (two years) and
- III. to examine the impact of exchange rate on petroleum pump price and to validate the newly improved model.

1.4 Significance of the study

As several literature has been produced on Modeling the Fluctuation of the Price of Crude Oil in Nigeria, modeling the fluctuation of the petroleum pump price (PMS) in Nigeria has not been investigated considerably. In modeling the realistic variation of PMS, and given the removal of subsidy in Nigeria, this research seeks to advance existing literature by formulating a practical time series model that will forecast future Petroleum pump price and its effect on the standard of living in Nigeria. Hence the government, Academia, Petroleum Marketers and every other stakeholder that make the policies will significantly benefit from this research. For the purpose of increasing economic growth and enhancing the standard of living of every Nigerian. And to stabilized the petroleum pump prices in Nigeria.

1.5 Scope of the study

The scope of this study is restricted to modeling the fluctuation of petroleum pump price (PMS) in the event of the petroleum subsidy removal in Nigerian and estimating the dynamic interrelationship between the Petroleum pump price and exchange rate.

MATERIAL AND RESEARCH METHOD

3.2 Research Methodology

This study used a case study of Nigeria, where the study targeted the macroeconomic activities concerning petroleum pump price volatility, its relationship with other macroeconomic variables, such as, exchange rate, and inflation rate. The study also takes into consideration the in-depth estimation of the fluctuation of petroleum pump prices, employs and effective model capable of predicting the future petroleum pump price and to also test the models 'efficiency and forecasting accuracy.

3.3 Data collection

The model for forecasting the petroleum pump price (PMS) in this study is developed using average monthly data of the petroleum pump price in Nigeria obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin/ data based, and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) statistical database, spanning the year January 1990 to December 2023. Hence the study will determine the effect of the Petroleum Pump price on inflation rate, and the relationship between petroleum pump price and exchange rate.

3.4 Jarque-Bera Test for Normality

Jargue-Bera is a joint test of Skewness and kurtosis that examines whether data series exhibit normal distribution or not. and this test was developed by Jargue and Bera (1980).

The test statistic is expressed as: $\frac{N}{6} [S^2 + \frac{(k-3)^2}{4}] \sim \chi^2$

3.5 The Stationary Test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test)

One of the most important assumptions in financial time series is the stationary of the data series. The unit root test, formerly referred to as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF), which employs a parametric autoregressive structure to capture serial correlation, can be used to verify this assumption. If a data series is not stationary, it should either be transformed or differentiated by figuring out the order of integration—that is, how many times it needs to be differentiated in order to become stationary. Dickey and Fuller (1979) proposed the unit root test, which is represented by the following:

Null hypothesis as $H_0: \varphi = 1$ and Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \varphi < 1$

Test Statistic (t-ratio): $\frac{\varphi_1^n - 1}{std(\varphi_1)} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T P_{t-1} \varepsilon_t}{\sigma^2 \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T P_{t-1}^2}}$

Where $\varphi_1 = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T P_{t-1} P_t}{\sum_{t=1}^T P_{t-1}^2}$, $\widehat{\varphi_2} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (P_t - \widehat{\varphi_1} P_{t-1})^2}{T-1}$

Where $P = 0$, and T is the sample size, ε_t is the error term at time t , P_t is the current data series, and P_{t-1} is the prior data series. If the estimated value of t exceeds the critical value of t , the null hypothesis is rejected.

3.6 Model Modification

To mitigate the effects of outliers related to the heavy-tailed distribution in the petroleum pump prices, it is possible to modify the GARCH model using GM-estimators enhancing the robustness of the model. Thus to extend the Tim work (1986) he should propose a better model to replace the current GARCH model which is not able to handle the outliers or the heavy tailed distribution as good as the ARCH or the current GARCH models. The process for the modification is as follows:

1. Standard GARCH Model Setup

The standard GARCH (1,1) model can be written as:

$$y_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t \quad \varepsilon_t = \sigma_t z_t$$

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$$

Where:

y_t Is the petroleum pump price at time t

σ_t^2 Is the conditional variance at time t

z_t Is the white noise process, assumed to be normally distributed ($z_t \sim N(0,1)$)

ω, α, β are the parameters to be estimated, with constraints $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha + \beta > 1$

2. GM-Estimators: Motivation

The standard GARCH model often assume normality, and does not account for heavy-tail distribution and outliers. The GM-estimator a robust estimator, offers robust alternative by minimizing the weight of outlier and improve the robustness of the model for heavy-tailed distributions. Therefore, to modify the GARCH model we choose the Weight Function for the GM-estimator.

3. The GM-estimators minimizes a robust objective function of the residuals $\rho(\varepsilon_t/\sigma_t)$ Instead of the square errors. In this study we choose the Huber's Loss function

Using Huber's function

$$\rho(\mu) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \mu^2 & \text{if } |\mu| \leq k \\ k|\mu| - \frac{1}{2} k^2 & \text{if } |\mu| > k \end{cases}$$

4. Modifying the Likelihood Function:

To implement GM-estimators, modify the log-likelihood function of the GARCH model by replacing squared residuals with the robust function ρ :

$$\rho; \quad L(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^T \left[\log(\sigma_t^2) + \rho\left(\frac{\varepsilon_t}{\sigma_t}\right) \right]$$

Where $\theta = (\beta, \alpha, \text{ and } \omega)$ are the GARCH parameters to be estimated

$\rho(\epsilon_t/\sigma_t)$ is the robust loss function applied to the standard residuals ϵ_t/σ_t

5. Parameter Estimation Using Iterative Re-Weighting:

a) Initialize parameters θ_0 and compute residuals $\epsilon_t = y_t - \mu_t$

b) Calculate Weights for each residual ω_t based on the derivatives of ρ Huber's function.

$$\omega_t = \frac{\varphi(\epsilon_t/\sigma_t)}{\epsilon_t/\sigma_t}$$

$$\text{Where } \varphi(\mu) = \frac{d}{du} \rho(\mu)$$

c) Update Parameters θ using weighted least squares ω_t .

d) Repeat step 2 & 3 until convergence. this modifies the error structures as; $Z_t \sim t(v)$

Where V is the degrees of freedom parameter controlling the tail thickness incorporate in the model

$$L(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^T \left[\log(\sigma_t^2) + \rho\left(\frac{\epsilon_t}{\sigma_t}\right); V \right]$$

The ρ_t is the robust parameter

6. Handling Heavy-Tailed Distributions: Use a heavy-tailed distribution like the student's t-distribution for z_t .

7. Final Model Specification: $\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha(\omega_{t-1} \epsilon_{t-1}^2) + \beta\sigma_{t-1}^2$

Where ω_{t-1} are the weighted function.

Therefore, the modification is making the GARCH model more robust and capable of capturing both outliers and heavy tails distribution properties of the petroleum pump price data.

Statistical Properties of the improved model

The properties of the improved model are: (ω, α, β) .

- Where the ω represent the intercept term of the constant in the variance equation
- α measure the reaction of conditional volatility to market shock
- β Measures the persistence of conditional volatility irrespective of market event. Higher indicated that volatility is more persistent overtime. It also captures long-term volatility effects or the tendency to remain elevated after shock.

The sum of , α and β ($\alpha + \beta$) is often interpreted as a measure of volatility persistence. If this sum is close 1, it indicated high persistence in volatility.

Where $\beta > \alpha$ indicated that long term volatility persistence effect is usually stronger that short-term shock.

Heteroscedasticity regression Model

3.7 Outlier Diagnosis Method

The Outliers Diagnostics Method based on Leverage points, as well as the Outliers Diagnostics Method. It is, therefore, based on the Residual Outliers that these. The performance of each method is evaluated in terms of the ability to characterize the outliers. These leverage points are identified by using the R Package program and the remaining outlier identification processes.

3.7.1 Leverage outliers Diagnostics Methods

Outliers with high leverage have a tendency to pull or have a higher influence on the model parameters that are used to estimate the regression line. One common method used in this study to determine whether our data is homogeneous or contains anomalous regions is to calculate the observations' Mahalanobis distance. The resilient outlier diagnostics of the Mahalanobis Distance (RMD), which is based on the Minimum Volume Ellipsoid (MVE), can be used to estimate the mean and covariance matrix (Rousseauw, 1987). Here's how to get it: $RMD =$

$$\sqrt{(X - T_R(X))' C_R(X)^{-1} (X - T_R(X))}$$

For $i = 1 \dots n$ where the reliable location and shape estimates of MVE are $T_R(X)$ and $C_R(X)$ to determine whether the point is significant in X-Space' alone, the robust distance from the Mahalanobis Distance using the MVE estimations of the mean and covariance matrix Can be compared to the $\chi_{p-1,0.957}^2$ distribution in this estimator. An observation will be classified as either of the two using this process, not as a high leverage outlier or

an outlier. When traditional distance measurement filter on a number of difficult multiple outlier data sets, this methodology performs interestingly.

3.7.2 Residual Outlier Diagnosis

A Suitable robust regression approach must also be used to diagnose outliers in order to acquire the regressor coefficient of the. Robust wildbootstrap method. It uses observed data's outliers to identify significant points, which aids in diagnosis. When dealing with univariate and multivariate data, the least median of squares (LMS) regression process, as outlined by Rousseeuw and Van Zomeren (1990), is a reliable method for identifying regression outliers. The LMS regression residuals are computed in order to obtain the regressor coefficient. The objective function's value multiplied by a finite sample correction factor that relies on n and p yields the estimated scaled residuals,

$$\text{which are represented as: } s^0 = \left(1 + \frac{5}{n-p}\right) \sqrt{\text{med}r_i^2}$$

Where $\text{med}r^2$ is the median of the square residuals, $r_1^2, r_2^2, \dots, r_n^2$ where n is the sample size and p is the number of regressor variables A regression outlier is identified at point $(y_{i1}, x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip})$ is the labelled as regression outlier if the corresponding standardized residual is larger. The estimate of the standardized residual of the ith vector regression model is deemed to be an outlier; this can be expressed as $(|r|/s) > 2.5$

3.8 Forecasting evaluation

It is necessary to evaluate the improved model efficacy since the financial and monetary authorities have to decide which evaluation criteria to use. In this manner to determine the improved Model's fit for reliable forecasting in compare to the existing ones. The Root absolute Error (RAE), Mean Square Error (MSE) and Root Mean square error (RMSE) will be used to access the model forecasting accuracy compare to the existing models. The following

is the forecasting error statistics: $\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |r_t^2 - \sigma_t^2|$ and $\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (r_t^2 - \sigma_t^2)^2}$ where n

the number of the fitted parameters, r_t^2 is the actual variance. And σ_t^2 is the square root of the conditional forecasting variance (Vee et al, 2009). The model with the least error statistics is the best model with forecasting ability or accuracy.

In addition, the forecasting accuracy and efficacy of the models to be used for comparison are the Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

TABLE: 4.1 DATA SUMMARY TABLE

	YEAR	PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE	INFLATION RATE	EXCHANGE RATE
MIN	2000	20.0	-2.490	98.97
1 ST QUARTER	2006	40.0	9.475	129.12
MEDIAN	2012	78.0	12.400	157.38
MEAN	2012	100.5	13.129	218.12
3 RD QUARTER	2017	145.3	16.262	305.88
MAXIMUM	2023	671.9	28.920	812.70

The above table: 4.1 shows the data summary for the study. The data is a monthly data generated from the National bureau of Statistics (NBS) and centra Bank of Nigeria (CBN) span the year 2000 to 2023. The minimum petroleum pump price was 20.0 naira, in the 1st quarter it rose to 9.475, with median price 100.00, the table shows an increase of the pump price a45.3 in the 3rd quarter and maximum petroleum pump price from the year 2000 to 2023 was 671.9 naira.

The minimum exchange rate of United State Dollar to Naira was 98.97 between 2000 to 2023, and increases to 129.12 in the 1st quarter, with 157.38 as the median exchange rate, with mean 218.12. where in the 3rd quarter the exchange rate increases to 305.88 and the maximum exchange rate value was closed at 812.70 between the year 2000 to 2023.

Outlier Diagnosis.

In time series forecasting, locating outliers is crucial because they affect the forecast model that forecast future values. The accuracy and dependability of the forecasts might be lowered by even a few outliers in the time series of a certain area. Outlier-filled areas, particularly those towards the beginning or end of the time series, can lead to

inaccurate forecasts. You may determine your degree of confidence in the predicted values at every point by identifying these locations.

In this regard, outlier diagnosis was undertaken to identify outliers in the data to identify the type and method of eliminating the outlier.

The boxplot for the data set is a standardized way of displaying the distribution of data based on five-number summary (minimum, first quartile, (Q1), median, Third quartile (Q3), and maximum.

The outlier (if any) is displayed as an individual point that is in excess of 1.5 times the inter-quartile range above the upper and below the lower quartiles.

FIG: 4.1

Any data point that is above $Q3 + 1.5IQR$ or below $Q1 - 1.5IQR$ in a boxplot is considered an outlier. The first and third quartiles are denoted by $Q1$ and $Q3$, respectively, while the interquartile range ($Q3 - Q1$) is represented by IQR.

The data on the petroleum pump price, exchange rate, and inflation rate showed some outliers, according to the box plots. Values that seem to be much higher or lower than other values in the dataset, or that fall below the boxplot's upper or lower whisker, are considered as outliers.

But it is important to know that not all outliers are to be eliminated, it is very crucial to know the cause of the outliers so as to make further decision on how to eliminate them. However, the outlier in this data is very important as they represent significant shift of trend or seasonality of the data.

These outliers represent legitimate data points, which do not occur due to measurement or entry error or other issues, instead, they are variables that represent policy change, such as the subsidy removal policy. Therefore, they should not be removed from the data set, but instead, they should be taken into account.

However, since the petroleum subsidy removal represent a permanent shift in the level of the petroleum pump price data, and other variables in the study, it is very necessary to consider using a method that can handle structural breaks and heavy-tailed distribution in the data set. In this manner, the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity GARCH model is an appropriate statistical technique for modeling time series data that exhibit volatility cluster.

Likewise, the GM-estimators method does not require the assumptions or normality errors, which by employing the incorporated GM-estimator-based GARCH model, the model will account for the structural breaks, heavy-tailed distribution and can be potential in leading to more accurate and robust estimates of the model parameters.

TABLE: 4.2

VARIABLES	MEAN	MEDIAN	SD	MIN	MAX
PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE	100.45635	78.00	99.770	20.00	671.86
INFLATION RATE	13.129	12.400	5.266	-2.49	28.92
EXXHANGE RATE	218.123	157.385	133.677	98.97	812.70

FIG: 4.2. Time Series plot for original data

Time Series Plots

TABLE: 4.3. STATIONARITY FOR VARIABLE IN THEIR ORIGINAL FORM

<i>Variable</i>	<i>ADF-Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Stationary</i>
<i>Petroleum Pump Price</i>	1.459228537	0.99	No
<i>Inflation Rate</i>	-3.748201178	0.022015941	Yes
<i>Exchange Rate</i>	1.779119681	0.99	No

Table: 4.3 show the Augmented Dickey-fuller (ADF) test for the three variables in their original form, where Petroleum Pump price with ADF = 1.4592, Lag order = 6 has a P-value 0.99, which is much higher than the typical significant level (0.05), suggests statistical evidence that the Null hypothesis of non-stationarity cannot be rejected. Which implies that the petroleum pump price data in its original form is likely non-stationary.

Where the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic for Inflation rate original data (-3.7482) is more negative than the critical values (1%, -2.86 at 5% and -2.57 at 10%) with p-value of 0.02202, which is less than the 0.05 level indicated strong statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity and conclude that the inflation rate data is likely stationary. Hence the Exchange rate data in the original form having ADF statistics of 1.779119681, and p-value 0.99, which is larger than the 0.05 level, indicated strong statistical evidence for not rejecting the null hypothesis of non-stationarity.

Since the petroleum pump price and exchange rate data are non-stationary, there is need to transform the data using differencing method in order to make them stationary.

TABLE: 4.4. VARIABLES AT FIRST DIFFERENCE

VARIABLE	ADF-STATISTIC	P-VALUE	STATIONARY
PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE	1.459228537	0.99	No
INFLATION RATE	-3.748201178	0.022015941	Yes
EXCHANGE RATE	1.779119681	0.99	No
PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE (1ST DIFFERENCING)	-2.725281062	0.270537223	No
EXCHANGE RATE (1ST DIFFERENCING)	-4.00639501	0.01	Yes
PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE (2ND DIFFERENCING)	-10.781,	0.01	Yes

Table: 4.4 shows Variables at first order differencing, where Exchange rate shows ADF-statistics -4.006395 with p-value of 0.01, which less than the 0.05 level. This clearly indicated exchange rate stationarity at 1st difference. The petroleum pump price 1st difference is still indicating non-stationarity with ADF: -2.725281062 and p-value of 0.2705 which is also greater than 0.05. The plot shows reduced trend but potential volatility clustering.

FIG: 4.3

Therefore, by proceeding to 2nd order differencing the results of the second-order differencing indicated Stationarity in the petroleum pump price with ADF of -10.781, Lag order = 6, and p-value of 0.01, which is less than the 0.05 level.

FIG: 4.4

Checking for ARCH effect in the data

TABLE: 4.5 ARCH RESULT

Variable	LM Statistic	LM p-value	F Statistic	F p-value
Petroleum Pump Price (2nd Diff)	73.8285	0.0004	9.6772	9.42
Inflation Rate	240.6265	0.0006	180.2652	4.83
Exchange Rate (1st Diff)	87.134	0.0008	12.2259	2.17

Table:4.5 shows the result for ARCH effect of the three variables, particularly, petroleum pump price, Inflation rate and exchange rate.

Petroleum Pump Price (Second Difference) indicated a test statistic of 73.8285, with p-value: 0.0004. The original data of Inflation rate which is Stationary, shows test statistic of 240.6265 and p-value: 0.0006. While exchange rate Exchange Rate is stationarity at First Difference indicated a test statistic of 87.1340 and a p-value of 0.0008.

In this manner three variables indicated an extremely low p-values (much smaller than the F-statistics and the conventional 0.05%). This indicates strong statistical evidence against the null hypothesis of no ARCH effects. The presence of ARCH suggests non-constant in volatility of the economic variables over time. The economic variables, instead exhibit clustering, where period of high volatility is followed by period of high volatility and low volatility is followed by low volatility period.

This volatility clustering is particularly strong in the Inflation Rate, as evidenced by its exceptionally low p-value and high-test statistic. The results imply that these economic variables experience periods of relative stability followed by periods of higher instability or fluctuations.

However, with the presence of ARCH effect in the variables, the result suggested that the application of GARCH models which accounts for time-varying volatility would be more appropriate than models that assume constant volatility.

Table: 4.6 Petroleum Pump Price Forecast for 2024 - 2025

DATE	FORECAST	LOWER_80	UPPER_80	LOWER_95	UPPER_95
1/1/2024	671.8680501	642.4979712	701.238129	626.8951167	716.8409834
2/1/2024	671.8680566	642.4700987	701.2660145	626.8524336	716.8836796
3/1/2024	671.8680631	642.4422527	701.2938735	626.8097909	716.9263353
4/1/2024	671.8680696	642.414433	701.3217063	626.7671886	716.9689507
5/1/2024	671.8680762	642.3866396	701.3495127	626.7246264	717.0115259
6/1/2024	671.8680827	642.3588724	701.377293	626.6821044	717.0540610
7/1/2024	671.8680892	642.3311313	701.4050471	626.6396224	717.0965560
8/1/2024	671.8680957	642.3034162	701.4327752	626.5971802	717.1390112
9/1/2024	671.8681022	642.2757271	701.4604774	626.5547778	717.1814267
10/1/2024	671.8681088	642.2480639	701.4881536	626.5124151	717.2238025
11/1/2024	671.8681153	642.2204265	701.515804	626.4700919	717.2661387
12/1/2024	671.8681218	642.1928149	701.5434287	626.4278081	717.3084355
1/1/2025	671.8681283	642.1652289	701.5710277	626.3855636	717.3506930

2/1/2025	671.8681348	642.1376686	701.5986011	626.3433584	717.3929113
3/1/2025	671.8681414	642.1101338	701.6261489	626.3011923	717.4350904
4/1/2025	671.8681479	642.0826245	701.6536713	626.2590651	717.4772306
5/1/2025	671.8681544	642.0551405	701.6811683	626.2169769	717.5193319
6/1/2025	671.8681609	642.0276819	701.7086399	626.1749274	717.5613944
7/1/2025	671.8681674	642.0002485	701.7360863	626.1329166	717.6034182
8/1/2025	671.8681739	641.9728404	701.7635075	626.0909444	717.6454035
9/1/2025	671.8681805	641.9454573	701.7909036	626.0490106	717.6873503
10/1/2025	671.868187	641.9180993	701.8182747	626.0071152	717.7292587
11/1/2025	671.8681935	641.8907663	701.8456207	625.9652581	717.7711289
12/1/2025	671.8682	641.8634582	701.8729419	625.9234391	717.8129610

Table: 4.6 Shows the future petroleum pump price forecast for the next twenty-four months ahead ranging from January 2024 to December 2025, including the point forecast and predicted intervals at 80% and 95% confidence level.

The GM-estimators-based GARCH model predicts a steady increase in petroleum pump price over the next two years. Which indicated that the at 95% prediction interval by December 2025 the forecast ranges from ₦625.9234391 to ₦717.8129610 per liter

Fig: 4.5

The Fig:4.5 displays the forecast for the next 24 months, including the prediction intervals.

Table 4.7 The results from GM-estimators GARCH (1,1) Model

Variables/Parameters	Coefficients	Std. error	Prob.
μ	48.78793*	3.651115	0.000000
ar1	0.99999997	0.000180	0.000000
ma1	0.025033	0.011401	0.028119
b_1	0.004842*	0.001613	0.002688
α_1	0.772146*	0.119995	0.000000
Φ	1.459135	0.000000	0.099979
α	2.117463*	0.015069	0.000000
The mean equation	$Y_t = 48.78793 + 0.9999997 * Y_{t-1} + 0.02503286 * \epsilon_{t-1}$		

The variance equation	$\hat{h}_t = 1.459135 + 0.773146 \times \hat{h}_{t-1} + 0.004842 \times \hat{u}_{t-1}^2$
Log likelihood	1084.571
Durbin-Waston stat	2.053007
Akaike information criterion (AIC)	-7.3941
Schwarz criterion (SC)	-7.4843
Hannan-Quinn criterion (HQ)	-7.4475

* =Statistically Significant at 1% Level

The table; present the breakdown of the statistical analysis result, with respect to the model parameters and diagnostics: where it shows that the Mean Equation suggested that the coefficients are positive and highly statistically significant (1% p-value) and the (μ) has a value 48.78793, with AR1 term: 0.9999997, and MA term which is 0.025033 On the other hand, by analyzing the conditional variance equation (h_t) can be confirmed that the coefficient of the constant variance term (φ) which is 1.459135 and the GARCH term (b_1): 0.004842 and the ARCH parameter (α_1): 0.772146 are positive, subunit and statistically significant at the 1% level of p-value.

This gives the results of the GM-estimators GARCH model. The time-varying volatility includes a constant ($\varphi = 2.117463$) plus its past value ($\alpha_1 = 0.772146$) and a component which depends on past errors ($b_1 = 0.004842$). Note that it took 0 iterations in R package to reach the convergence (*Log likelihood* = 1084.571) and all the coefficients of the estimated conditional variance (h) specification meet the stability conditions: $0 < b_1 < 1$; $0 < \theta_1 < 1$ and $b_1 + \theta_1 < 1$.

Evaluation Matrix

Table 4.8 The Forecast Results

MODEL	RMSE	MAE	MSE
Modified Model	20.2163	3.5454	408.6988

Table:4.4 display the evaluation result which shows that the Gm-estimators GARCH model is fitted to forecast the future petroleum pump price volatility, having a lower RMSE of 20.2163, MSE of 3.5454 and MSE value of 408.69888. this gives the idea of the model's forecasting efficacy. The RMSE value of 20.2163 signifies that, on average, in forecasting for the future petroleum pump price volatility, the models' forecasting deviate from the actual values by 20 units. The high RMSE relative to the mean (μ) also suggest that there is considerable volatility in the petroleum pump prices that the model is capturing.

Table: 4.9 Weighted Ljung-Box Test on standardized residuals.

Lag	Statistics	P-value
1	0.01605	0.8992
5	0.04935	1.0000
9	0.08340	1.0000

D.O.F = 2

The table shows the serial correlation in the residuals, whether the residuals are independent over time. In this manner, the high values of the P-value of all lag which appear to be greater than 0.05 indicated that we there is enough statistical evidence not to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting there is no significant serial correlation in the residuals.

The Autocorrelation Function (ACF) plots of standardized residuals of the GM-estimators GARCH model of petroleum pump price shows that the X-axis lags from January 2024 to December 2025, which is 24 months ahead forecast. The graph shows that most bars are within the significant threshold, which is a good sign that suggest that the model was able to capture most of the correlation in the data. The graph indicated no obvious pattern of decaying autocorrelation or seasonality which is generally good for residuals.

Generally, the ACF plot suggests that the GM-estimators GARCH model has done a reasonably good job of capturing the autocorrelation structure in the petroleum pump price data. Most lag appears to be not significant. Evidence from the ACF also support the adequacy of the GM-estimators GARCH models is capturing most of the systematic patters in the petroleum pump price data.

Table: 4.10 Weighted ARCH LM test for the GM-estimators-GARCH

LAG	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
3	0.007367	0.9316**
5	0.017782	0.9989**
7	0.026601	1.0000**

Table 4.10. shows the presence of ARCH effect (autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity). Where the high P-values indicated that is no significant ARCH effect, suggesting that the GM-estimators-GARCH model was able to capture the volatility in the data and that it the model does not suffer from conditional heteroskedasticity. This also indicated goodness of fit of the model.

Tabl:4.11 comparisons of model Forecasting efficacy

The Table:4.11 displays the model comparisons of forecasting accuracy, where GM-estimators GARCH model has a

MODEL	RMSE	MAE	MSE	Rank
The improved model (GM-estimators GARCH)	20.2163	3.5454	408.6988	1
Traditional GARCH	27.03035	5.434599	730.6397	3
ARCH	20.58014	3.711069	423.5423	2
Random Forest	42.00948	8.513515	1764.7961	4

MAE and RMSE of 3.5454 and 20.2163, the Traditional GARCH model has a MAE and RMSE of 5.434599 and 27.03035, ARCH model has a MAE and RMSE of 3.711069 and 20.58014, and the Random Forest Model having a value of 8.513515 and 42.00948 of MAE and RMSE. This indicated that the GM-estimators GARCH model has the lowest MAE and RMSE, indicating that the model has the best forecasting accuracy among the models evaluated. The evaluation also suggests that, the GM-estimators GARCH model has smaller error on average compared to others models.

Table:4.12 PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE VS. EXCHANGER RATE RESIDUALS

Min	1Q	Median	Mean	3q	Max
-37.149	-10.82	1.306		9.377	269.635
Outliers' weight					
0.02791	0.80240	0.94640		0.97160	0.99840

TABLE: 4.13. INFLATION RATE VS PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE

RESIDUALS					
Min	1Q	Median	Mean	3q	Max
-13.16797	-2.8871	-0.3077	0.89760	2.8782	16.9779
Outliers 'weights					
0.06627	0.88460	0.95320		0.98520	0.99880

Table:4.12 from the top displays the distribution of differences between predicted values and the actual values. The minimum value of the difference is -37.149, first quarter: -10.82 and the median difference between the predicted and actual value is 1.306. the 3rd quarter is shown to be 9.377, where the maximum difference is 269.635.

From the Robust weight, 9 observations are identified as outliers with zero weight, where 12 observations have weights close to 1. The remaining 267 observations out of 288 observations have weight ranging from 0.02791 to 0.99840. Likewise, the distribution of the difference between the observed and the predicted values of the Inflation rate, shows values with Minimum residual: -13.1697, 1Q value -2.887, median residual as -0.3077, with mean 0.89760, where the 3rd quarter is 2.8782 and a maximum difference of 16.9779. this indicated a fairly balanced around zero, with some outliers on both end of the distribution of the residuals. The robustness weights shows that 18 observations are weighted approximately 1, where the remaining 270 are weights have a minimum of 0.06627, a mean of 0.89760 and a maximum of 0.99880, where the lower weighted indicated outliers or influential points on the model Weight.

Table: 4.14. Petroleum pump price vs Exchange rate Coefficients

	ESTIMATE	STD ERROR	T-VALUE PR(> t)
INTERCEPT	-22.73981	3.61535	-6.291.19e - 09***
EXCHANGE RATE	0.52290	0.01832	28.54 < 2e-16 ***
ROBUST RESIDUAL	12.56		
MULTIPLE R-SQAURE	0.9169		
ADJUSTED R-SQAURE	0.9166		

Table:4.14. Inflation rate vs Petroleum Pump price: Coefficients

	ESTIMATE	STD ERROR	T-VALUE PR(> t)
INTERCEPT	10.13333	0.40247	25.18 < 2e - 16***
PETROLEUM PUMP PRICE	0.02732	0.00176	15.52 < 2e-16***
ROBUST RESIDUAL	4.204		
MULTIPLE R-SQAURE	0.3014		
ADJUSTED R-SQAURE	0.2989		

Table:4.14 which is the coefficient table of the petroleum pump price shows the Intercept having an estimate of -22.7391(p<0.001) and exchange rate has a coefficient of 0.52290(p<0.001). both coefficients appear to be highly significant (indicated by ***). The robust residual standard error:12.56.

The Multiple R-squared with standard error 0.9169 indicated that about 91.7% of the variance in petroleum pump price is explained by the exchange rate. The adjusted R-squared also indicated 91.67%.

In Table:4.15 for the Inflation rate the intercept has a coefficient estimated as 10.13333, std error of 0.40247, and t-value which is equal to 25.18 Pr(|t|) < 2e-16. Where the coefficient indicates the intercept (10.13333) is the average estimate of the Inflation rate when the petroleum pump price is zero, Where the coefficient of the petroleum pump price estimated at 0.02732 indicated that for every 10% increase in the petroleum pump prices, there a likely increase with about 0.2% as well.

However, the Robust residual standard error is 4.204, where the adjusted R-squared is 0.2989, with Multiple R-squared of the model valued at 0.3014, which indicated that approximately 30.14% of the variability in the Inflation rate can be explained or accounted for by the petroleum pump price.

Generally, the overall analysis to examine the relationship between petroleum pump price and exchange rate, or in other word to determine the impact of exchange rate on petroleum pump price show a significant positive relationship and impact of the exchange rate on petroleum pump price return, as for every 10% increase in exchange rate. Petroleum pump price increases by 5.2%. The model also fit the well with high R-squared of 91.67%, despite the fact that some outliers existed, but the use of robust regression technique helps mitigate the influence of these outliers on the model estimates. Equally,

Fig: 4.8 the scatter plot illustrates the relationship between exchange rate and petroleum pump price which indicated a clear upward trend, indicated by the red line, which signifies that in any increase in the exchange, the petroleum pump price also rise as well. Meaning there is a positive relationship between the two macroeconomic variables between the exchange rate and petroleum pump price which align with the results of Dickey, D. A., & Fuller, W. A. (1979), Kilian, L. (2008), Akram, Q.F (2009), Zhang, D., & Broadstock, D. C. (2018), Coudert, V., Mignon, & Penot, A. (2008) and Reboredo, J. C. (2012). The relationship between the variables appears to be linear, as most data points clustering close to the trend line.

The distribution of the data illustrated that majority of the data points are concentrated in the lower exchange rate range below 400, with fewer observations at higher exchange rate. Several notable outliers, particularly at the higher end of the exchange rate spectrum which is around 800, where the petroleum prices are significantly higher than the trend line would predict.

In particular, the tight clustering of the data points around the trend line signifies the exchange rate is a good predictor of petroleum pump prices, aligning with the R-squared value (0.9169) previously displayed in table: 4.8. finally, the strong relationship implies that changes in exchange rate could as well have a significant impact on petroleum pump prices.

From the graph above, the exchange rates seem to range from 0 – 800, while the petroleum pump price range from 0 to 700

Inflation rate and petroleum pump price

Fig: is a scatter plot illustrate the relationship between petroleum pump price and Inflation rate. The plot indicated a clear positive trend which indicates that as petroleum pump price increase, Inflation rate tend to increase as well which align with the findings of Balachand, O. J., & Gali, J. (2007), Hamilton, J. D. (2009), Hooker, M.A. (2002), Barsky, R. B., & Kilian L. (2004), and Liu, L., & Morley, B. (2011). The scatter plots indicated a spread of data points clustered in the lower left quadrant of the graph, suggesting that most observations occur at lower petroleum price and lower inflation rate. Likewise, several outlier points exist, particularly at higher petroleum prices, which is during the subsidy removal regime, that deviate significantly from the general trend. The relationship between Inflation rate and petroleum pump price doesn't appear to be strictly linear. The analysis indicates that there is more

variability in inflation rates at lower petroleum pump prices. The petroleum pump prices range from 0 to 700 naira, where Inflation rate ranges from 0 to 30%.

Generally, in comparison between the two robust regression models to test the Interplay between Exchange rate and petroleum pump price which is Model 1, and to examine the impact of petroleum pump price on Nigerian's standard of living (Inflation rate).

Model1. Indicated a significant positive relationship between petroleum pump price and exchange rate, where the model explains a high proportion of 91.69% of the variability in the petroleum pump price.

Model 2. There is a significant positive impact of the petroleum pump price on the Nigerians standard of living (Inflation rate), but the model only account for 30.14% of the variability in inflation rate. This strongly indicated that, aside from the petroleum pump price there are other macroeconomic variable and policies that have significant impact on the inflation rate.

CONCLUSION

Statistical modeling has been extensively utilized in financial market for decision-making as a safety net, developing models for risk prediction and mitigation, identifying trends and pattern in financial markets, forecasting future economic conditions, interpreting financial data and generating insight for rick management. However, volatility in financial market have attracted the attention of several researchers, where more and more specialists and researchers are concerned with finding and using the most appropriate and accurate methods for estimating this volatility.

As a result of the increased volatility in macroeconomic data, it is currently becoming more and more difficult to assess risk-specific indicators across uncertainty and unpredictable period of time filled with a multitude of facts and occurrences. Excessive volatility resulting from irregular variation can make forecasting more difficult and unreliable, mask underlying trends and seasonal patterns, lessen the efficacy of conventional time series models, produce data outliers, and necessitate the employment of more complex and Robust modeling techniques. The event of the petroleum subsidy removal in Nigeria has causes an irregular variation, uncertainty, unusual observations and period of high volatility in the petroleum pump price data ranging from May 2023 to date. In this regard proper and accurate modeling and forecasting of the petroleum pump price data is very crucial in risk management and policy making. Therefore, the goal of this study was to modify a GM-estimators GARCH model for forecasting the future petroleum pump price data volatility

The result form the analysis shows that the GM-estimators GARCH model has forecasting accuracy and outperform the ARCH, Traditional GARCH and Random Forest model in forecasting accuracy. In addition, the exchange rate has a possible impact on the petroleum pump price which in every 10% increase in the exchange rate, there is likely 5.2% percent increase in the petroleum pump price as well, which findings aligned with the findings of (Titus and Abdulkadir, 2020; Despite Atoi's., 2014; and Patti and Ratti.,2007) and that change in price of petrol affect the economy. Hence about 91.7% of the variance in petroleum pump price is explained by the exchange rate. The study also suggest that petroleum pump price have a positive impact on Nigerian interest rate, in which the petroleum pump price account for 30% of the variability in the Inflation rate. This study was limited to the consideration of three variables which are: the petroleum pump price, inflation rate and exchange rate, and uses the official average monthly petroleum pump price for the year 2000 to 2023. Though, the petroleum pump price differs with respect to regional differences, where transportation cost is also applied to the pump price, in this manner, there are other variables that might have significant influence on the petroleum pump price, therefore, this study suggests further research that would consider additional variable like petroleum transportation cost.

RECOMMENDATION

Petroleum is one of the major sources of Nigerian revenue as its contributed to 70% of the revenue generated.

However, the increase in petroleum pump price has serious positive impact on the standard of living as petroleum consumption is needed in Nigeria for daily activities, in this regard some of the recommendations of this study are:

- I. The government should encourage local refineries like Dangote to enhance their capacity and efficiency, this will eliminate the impact of exchange rate volatility by reducing dependency on importation of petroleum.
- II. The implementation of the subsidy removal program to minimized the negative impact of the petroleum pump price on the Nigerians standard of living
- III. Policies aims at stabilizing the exchange rate by diversifying the economy, increasing foreign exchange, inflation management and exchange rate stability which could could help the petroleum pump price more predictable should be implemented by the government.

- IV. The government should embark of necessary strategies of creating and maintaining petroleum reserves that can provide buffer against global crude oil price volatility. This reserve can help in stabilizing domestic petroleum pump prices in times of global market disruption
- V. Government should improve efficiency of the petroleum distribution network; this can reduce cost and stabilize petroleum prices. Investment, infrastructure and combating illegal activities such as oil thefts and pipe vandalism can contribute to price stability.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adedipe, B. (2004). The Impact of Oil on Nigeria's Economic Policy Formulation. Paper presented at the conference on Nigeria: Maximizing Pro-poor Growth, organized by Overseas Development Institute in conjunction with Nigerian Economic Summit Group, June 16-17.
- 2) Ademola, I. S., & Ajayi, E. O. (2019). The Impact of Petroleum Pump Price on Exchange Rate Volatility in Nigeria. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 9(4), 320-332.
- 3) Akinwale, Y., Akanbi, B., Adetunji, B., & Olatunji, E. (2013). The Economic Effects of Gradual Removal of Petroleum Subsidies in Nigeria. *Energy Policy*, 58, 295-303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.02.029>
- 4) Amano, R. A., & Van Norden, S. (1995). Exchange Rates and Oil Prices. *Review of International Economics*, 3(3), 278-291.
- 5) Atanu, E., Etuk, E., & Amos, E. (2021). Comparison of ARIMA and GARCH Models in Forecasting Crude Oil Price Volatility. *Journal of Economics and Financial Analysis*, 4(2), 45-61.
- 6) Azaiki, S. (2007). Oil, gas and life in Nigeria. Yenagoa: Ibadan Spectrum Books Limited.
- 7) Barrieu, P., & Ren, Z. (2017). Robust Value-at-Risk estimation using GM-GARCH models. *Quantitative Finance*, 17(7), 1075-1094.
- 8) Beum-jo Park (2022). Robust GARCH Models in the Presence of outliers: An application to Stock Return Volatility. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 67, 147-171.
- 9) Boitumelo Nnoi Yolanda Sekati, Johannes Tshepiso Tsoku & Lebotsa Daniel Metsileng | (2020) Modelling the Oil Price Volatility and Macroeconomic Variables in South Africa using the Symmetric and Asymmetric GARCH Models, *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 8:1, 1792153, DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2020.1792153
- 10) Bollerslev, T. (1986). Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity. *Journal of Econometrics*, 31(3), 307-327.
- 11) Borenstein, S., Cameron, A. C., & Gilbert, R. (1997). Do Gasoline Prices Respond Asymmetrically to Crude Oil Price Changes? *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 112(1), 305-339.
- 12) Cheke, D. I., Adeleke, I., & Olufemi, A. (2011). The Impact of Rising Petroleum Prices on Job Creation and Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs). *Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 9(3), 112-125.
- 13) Deebom, Z. D., Essi, I. D., & Igbudu, U. (2017). Modeling Price Volatility of Nigerian Crude Oil Markets Using GARCH Models: 1987-2017. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(1), 42-55.
- 14) Dharam, G. (1991). *The economics of oil and gas*. Cambridge University Press.
- 15) Doguwa, I., & Alade, F. (2023). The Impact of Petrol Subsidy Removal on Nigeria's Public Transportation and Inflation. *African Journal of Economics*, 18(1), 67-80.
- 16) Engle, R. F., & Gonzalez-Rivera, G. (1991). Semiparametric ARCH models. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 9(4), 345-359.
- 17) Engle, R. F., & Manganelli, S. (2004). CAViaR: Conditional autoregressive value at risk by regression quantiles. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 22(4), 367-381.
- 18) Entesar Hamed I. Eliwa, Amr Mohamed El Koshiry, Tarek Abd El-Hafeez, and Ahmed Omar (2024) Optimal Gasoline Price Predictions: Leveraging the ANFIS Regression Model. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*. Volume 2024, Article ID 8462056, 20 pages
- 19) Federer, J. (1996). Oil price volatility and the macroeconomy. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 11(3), 315-329.
- 20) Franses, P. H., & Ghijssels, H. (1999). Additive outliers, GARCH and forecasting volatility. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 15(1), 1-9.
- 21) Gasper, L., Santos, M., & Silva, E. (2023). Forecasting crude oil prices in an atypical environment: A Box-Jenkins approach. *Energy Economics*, 117, 106523.

- 22) Ghaffar, A., Aslam, U., & Zardari, Z. (2024). Gauging the Fuel Price Volatility using GARCH Models. *International Journal of Emerging Business and Economic Trend*, 2(2), 115-121. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.24732.91521
- 23) Godfred, K. A., & Kobina, A. (2012). Macroeconomic impact of oil price changes in Ghana: Forecast and analysis. *African Economic Review*, 6(2), 75-90.
- 24) Guo, H., & Kliesen, K. (2005). Oil price volatility and US macroeconomic activity. *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Review*, 87(6), 669-683.
- 25) Hamilton, J. D. (2008). Understanding crude oil prices. *The Energy Journal*, 29(2), 179- 206.
- 26) Hooker, M. A. (1999). Oil and the macroeconomic revisited. *Federal Reserve Board of Governors, Finance and Economics Discussion Series*, 1999-43.
- 27) Huber, P. J., & Ronchetti, E. M. (2009). Robust statistics (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- 28) Jiang, H., & Xu, L. (2023). A hybrid ARIMA-LSTM model for petroleum pump price forecasting in China. *Energy*, 270, 127334.
- 29) Jin, G. (2008). The impact of oil price shock and exchange rate volatility on economic growth: A comparative analysis for Russia, Japan, and China. *Research Journal of International Studies*, 8(11), 98-111.
- 30) Ledolter, J. (1989). The effect of additive outliers on the forecasts from ARIMA models. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 5(2), 231-240.
- 31) Mehara, P. (2008). Oil price volatility: Causes and impacts. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 22(2), 157-172.
- 32) Meludu, N. T., Obidiebube, E. A., Chukwu, O., & Ikeogu, C. F. I. (2023). Sustainable agriculture, nature
- 33) Meludu, Nkiru T., Komolafe, O. J. and Chika, P.C. (2023) Influence of Fuel Subsidy Removal on the Prices of Major Food Commodities in Southeastern Nigeria. *West African Journal of Sustainable Development*. Vol. 1
- 34) Monday, E. T., & Ahmed, A. (2020). Modeling the volatility of crude oil price in Nigeria using ARCH and ARCH-M models. *Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 10(4), 120-135.
- 35) Mork, K. A., Olsen, O., & Mysen, H. T. (1994). Oil prices and the international economy: Revisiting the linkages. *Energy Journal*, 15(4), 67-85.
- 36) Mwanakatwe, P. K., Daniel, J., & Nzungu, K. R. (2023). Forecasting oil price volatility dynamics using Hosten models. *African Journal of Financial Economics*, 12(1), 102-118.
- 37) National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). Data Bulletin: Nigeria's crude oil exports for Q3 2021. *National Bureau of Statistics*. Retrieved from <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- 38) Ngerebo-a, T. A., & Ibe, R. C. (2013). Exchange rate and macroeconomic performance in Nigeria: A causal post structural adjustment programme investigation. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 13(7), 43-48. .
- 39) Nigerian Central Bank. (2010). *Annual Economic Report*. Central Bank of Nigeria.
- 40) Nwoko, I. C., Ihemeje, J. C., & Anumadu, E. (2016). The impact of monetary policy on the economic growth of Nigeria. *African Research Review*, 10(3), 192-206.
- 41) Ocheni, S. I. (2015). Impact of fuel price increase on the Nigerian economy. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), 560.
- 42) Olaleye, S. S. (2022). Nigeria's petroleum industry and its contribution to national development. *African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 10(2), 120-134.
- 43) Olorunfemi, S. (2010). The effects of petroleum price hikes on Nigerian consumers. *Journal of Energy and Environment*, 7(1), 45-59.
- 44) Olugbenga, A. A., et al. (2017). Oil price volatility and economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(7), 70-81.
- 45) Philip, E. O., & Akintoye, W. (2006). The volatility of petroleum pump prices in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 24(3), 54-66.
- 46) Rousseeuw, P. J., & Leroy, A. M. (2005). Robust regression and outlier detection. John Wiley & Sons.
- 47) Sanni, M. I. (2014). Petroleum subsidy issues and the instability of prices in Nigeria. *Journal of African Economic Studies*, 5(2), 98-110.
- 48) Sofianos,E.; Zaganidis, E.; Papadimitriou, T.; Gogas, P. (2024) Forecasting East and West Coast Gasoline Prices with Tree-Based Machine Learning Algorithms. *Energies* 2024, 17, 1296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17061296>

- 49) Spiro, P. S. (1990). The impact of interest rate changes on stock price volatility. *Journal of Portfolio Management*, 16(2), 63-68.
- 50) Usman, I., Ikemefuna, E., & Fatima, S. (2015). The Nigerian petroleum sector and its role in economic growth. *Nigerian Economic Review*, 43(6), 89-105.
- 51) Victoria U., Esther C., Doris O. Onwa, David M.E. (2017) The Political economy of fuel subsidy Removal in Nigeria. *African Journal of Politics and Administrative Studies*, Vol. 9, 1
- 52) Xin James He (2023) Forecasting Gasoline Price with Time Series Models. Management Information Systems Commons. *International Information Management Association (IIMA)* .